

ISSUES AND SOLUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BUDGET PROGRAMS BY MINISTRIES AND AGENCIES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the problems that arise in the process of developing budget programs by first-level budget allocating organizations and explores ways to address them. The advantages and disadvantages of developing and approving budget and extra-budgetary expenditures in the context of budget programs are evaluated from a theoretical and legal perspective.

In accordance with Resolution No. 4 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 4, 2024, the methodology for developing, monitoring, and evaluating the effectiveness of budget and extra-budgetary expenditures of first-level budgetary organizations by budget programs has been established.

For 2025, the budget expenditures of the Ministry of Economy and Finance and the Ministry of Agriculture for 2025–2027 were approved on a pilot basis in the context of budget and extra-budgetary programs according to this regulation.

An analysis of the funds required for the implementation of the budget programs of the above-mentioned ministries shows that each subprogram includes expenditures of the ministries' departments and divisions such as:

- salaries and equivalent payments of employees (Group 1 expenditures),
- payroll deductions (Group 2 expenditures),
- other expenditures (Group 4 expenditures).

The Group 1 and Group 2 expenditures of subprograms were formed according to the staff schedule, while Group 4 expenditures were financed using a per capita funding method.

For example, in the subprogram “Tax and Customs Policy and Revenue Forecasting” under the “Fiscal Policy and Budget Sustainability” program, 2.435 million soums were allocated for paper purchases for 30 employees. If 75 million soums were allocated for this expense item for the entire ministry with 924 staff units, the calculation was made as follows: $(75 \text{ million soums} / 924) \times 30 = 2.435 \text{ million soums}$.

Given that this is an initial pilot phase in forming budget programs, this approach can be considered positive. However, in the future, it is advisable to form each type of expenditure

based on the actual expenditures of the previous year or on specific funding requests submitted by departments.

It is also observed that ministries and agencies form their budget programs in two main types.

For example, according to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the State Budget for 2025”:

- 12,587.6 soums were allocated for current expenditures of the Committee on the Development of Competition and Protection of Consumer Rights;
- 12,127.1 billion soums for current expenditures of the Agency for Management of State Assets;
- 312,492 soums for current expenditures of the Ministry of Justice;
- 169,396.9 soums for current expenditures of the Tax Committee.

These ministries and agencies have not developed development programs, so their allocations are provided only for current expenditures.

Meanwhile, under the same law, 55,154,225,6 soums were allocated to the Ministry of Preschool and School Education for current expenditures, including 6,331,679 soums for 11 development programs; and 4,039,733.2 soums were allocated to the Ministry of Health for current expenditures, including 1,676,853.5 soums for 22 development programs.

Thus, relevant funds have been allocated for ministries with development programs.

This situation may lead to certain difficulties in forming budget programs for ministries that have and do not have development programs.

In ministries with development programs, it is possible to form development programs as subprograms or activities.

For example, within the “Maternal and Child Health Protection” budget program of the Ministry of Health, the following development programs can be considered as subprograms:

- expenditures related to child vaccination;
- expenditures for the protection of maternal and infant health, and for strengthening reproductive health;
- expenditures for providing children, women of reproductive age, pregnant and breastfeeding women with preventive medications free of charge;
- expenditures for essential medicines and medical supplies (e.g., Vitamin K, surfactant, etc.) for protecting maternal and child health and reproductive-age women;
- expenditures for cochlear implant operations for children with hearing impairments (development programs).

Conversely, in ministries and agencies that lack development programs, their current expenditures should be formed as budget programs based on their strategic goals.

For example, the “Administrative Management Program” of the Ministry of Economy and Finance requires 117.8 billion soums, of which 65.4 billion soums are extra-budgetary funds.

The execution of this program includes employee salaries, equivalent payments, payroll deductions, and other (Group 4) expenditures.

Based on the 2025 experience of developing budget programs in the Ministry of Economy and Finance and the Ministry of Agriculture, several recommendations have been developed:

avoid duplication in the text part of budget programs;
focus on quality rather than quantity when setting target indicators;
limit the number of subprograms under a single program to no more than five;
ensure program titles are concise and informative, clearly indicating the types of products and/or outcomes the program aims to achieve, with reference to result types, clients, or program objectives to provide a clear understanding of its content.

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